

that short-duration line for eight generations. A new CMS line was named Zaoxian A in 1989.

Zaoxian A is still classified as a WA type. It is semidwarf (68 cm tall), averages 104 spikelets/panicle, with a 1,000-grain weight of 26.0 g. It also has long (1.62 m), well-exserted (73.5%) stigma, and its outcrossing rate is high (55.3%).

In 1990, we crossed Zaoxian A with three long-duration restorer lines, and tested yield capacity in a field experiment in Chengdu. Plots (2.5 m²) were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

The period to heading of F₁s related to Zaoxian A was about 20 d shorter than those of the restorer lines and shorter than the mid-parent values (see table). The period to heading of F₁s related to other CMS lines was about 10 d longer than the mid-parent values and longer than those of the restorer lines.

Days to heading of CMS lines, restorer lines, and F₁s, and growth duration and grain yield of F₁s.^a

Hybrid combination	Days to heading				Growth duration (d)	t/ha	Grain yield		
	P ₁	P ₂	Mid-parent value	F ₁			Percentage compared to		
							Check 1	Check 2	Check 3
Zaoxian A/R ₁	78	111	94.5	90	127	9.6	112	121	113
Zaoxian A/R ₂	78	113	95.5	92	128	9.4	110	119	111
Zaoxian A/R ₃	78	115	96.5	92	128	9.2	108	116	108
Zhen Shan 97 A/R ₁ (check 1)	75	111	93.0	112	148	8.6	100		
Zhen Shan 97 A/R ₄ (check 2)	75	88	81.5	92	130	8.0		100	
V20 A/R ₅ (check 3)	75	87	81.0	90	127	8.5			100

^aR₁ = Minghui 63, R₂ = 086, R₃ = Mingdian 501, R₄ = Zhalyeqing 8, R₅ = Ce 64. P₁ = CMS line, P₂ = restorer line. Check 1 and check 3 are the national checks of China and check 2 is the provincial check of Sichuan Province in the regional test of hybrid rice.

This indicates that days to heading of restorer lines is dominant over that of CMS lines Zhenshan 97 A and V20 A. Days to heading of Zaoxian A was incompletely dominant over that of the restorer lines.

Grain yields of hybrid combinations derived from Zaoxian A were higher than yields of national check Shanyou 63, although hybrid growth durations were

about 20 d shorter than that of Shanyou 63. Yields were significantly higher than those of Shanzhai 8 and Weiyou 64, which had almost the same growth durations as the hybrids.

The short duration of Zaoxian A appears to be incompletely dominant over the long duration of restorer lines, making Zaoxian A valuable for rice production and for hybrid rice breeding. □

Natural outcrossing on two cytoplasmic male sterile lines in northern India

J. S. Bijral, T. R. Sharma, B. B. Gupta, K. Singh, and C. L. Raina, SKUAST, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), R.S. Pura 181102, India

We studied the extent of outcrossing in cytoplasmic male sterile (A) lines RR988 A and RR39 A (CMS-WA cytoplasm developed at Pura, Jammu, and Kashmir). The cytosterile lines were surrounded by a single row of their

Seed set on 2 cytosterile lines at RARS, R.S. Pura, India, 1989 wet season.

A line	B line	Planting ratio	Grains/panicle (no.)		Total grains (no.)	Mean seed set (%)
			Filled	Unfilled		
RR988 A	CH988	1:1	68	850	918	7.4
RR39 A	K39	1:1	142	1101	1243	11.0

respective maintainer (B) lines (CH988 and K39). Plant spacing was 20 × 30 cm.

To synchronize flowering and prolong the pollen supply, maintainer lines were seeded 3 d earlier and 4 d later than the cytosterile (A) lines. All lines were transplanted at the same time, at 2 seedlings/hill. The flag leaves of the

cytosterile lines were not clipped.

The main panicles of 10 randomly selected plants of each cytosterile line were harvested individually and filled and unfilled grains/panicle counted. Outcrossing rate was low, probably because of poor panicle exertion of cytosterile lines (see table). □

Yield potential

Screening rice varieties and breeding lines for internode elongation ability under field conditions

R. V. Singh, Crop Research Station (CRS), Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, Uttar Pradesh (UP); J. L. Dwivedi (present address: Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division, IIRI); and O. P. Verma, CRS, Ghagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, UP, India

We evaluated 155 varieties and experimental lines for internode elongation ability under field conditions. Entries were seeded 13 Apr 1989 in two 5-m rows, 25 cm apart.

Water depth reached 190 cm the first week of Oct. Plant height, number and length of internodes, kneeling ability, maturity, and phenotypic acceptability were observed. Maximum length of three consecutive elongated internodes was derived from the sums of three adjacent internodes.

Seventy-four entries failed to produce grain. Among surviving entries, 17 produced 9-12 internodes, with total internode lengths of 126-215 cm (see table). These lines also had much better kneeling ability.

Maturity ranged from the last week of Nov to the first week of Dec. Locally popular variety Jalmagna matured the first week of Dec, 233 d after seeding.

While Jalmagna was highest in total internode elongation, four other entries exceeded its maximum three consecutive

internode elongation (see figure). Length of maximum elongating three adjacent internodes ranged from 54 to 93 cm. It took an average of 13.6 d for one internode to form (computed as number of days between start of flooding and flowering, divided by total number of elongated internodes). An estimate of

number of days required for maximum elongation of three adjacent internodes is 41 d. These internodes were probably formed during the highest water stagnation period starting the first week of Oct.

The maximum elongation of three adjacent internodes gives an indication of capacity for elongation in a prolonged

period of rapidly rising water, in this case 190-200 d from seeding. Elongation of the central internode of the longest three internodes (position 3-5 counting from the top of the figure) may correspond to the onset of water 40 d before flowering and/or to the extra stimulus to internode growth at panicle initiation, which was also 30-40 d before flowering. Further experiments using a group of varieties with a wider spread of flowering dates may help distinguish between these two causes.

Number of elongated internodes and maximum elongating three adjacent internodes may be used to assess promising lines for elongation ability. Further study is needed to determine the relationship between elongation ability and yield potential. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Performance of promising lines under natural field conditions in Uttar Pradesh, India.

Promising lines		Plant height (cm)	Internodes		Days to maturity	Date of maturity
Designation	Parentage		no.	Length (cm)		
IR45478-B-3	Baisbish/IR 19245-76-2- 1-3-3	167	12	126	239	8 Dec
NDGR87-2	Jalmagna/Sona	217	9	126	237	6 Dec
NDGR87-2-1-3	Jalmagna/Sona	220	9	127	245	14 Dec
NDGR87-104-2-1	Jalmagna/Sona	232	9	139	234	3 Dec
NDGR87-2-1-1	Jalmagna/Sona	232	9	142	237	6 Dec
NDGR87-104-2-3	Jalmagna/Sona	225	9	143	237	6 Dec
IR45478-B-4	Baisbish/IR19245-76-2-1-3-3	223	10	146	239	8 Dec
IR45468-15-GR-5	Baisbish/IR56	232	10	149	238	7 Dec
NDGR1045-125-103	RP/LMN111	238	10	160	236	5 Dec
NDGR87-104-1-3	Jalmagna/Sona	238	10	166	234	3 Dec
IR45468-B-10	Baisbish/IR56	237	10	168	240	9 Dec
IR45468-B-11	Baisbish/IR56	248	11	180	240	9 Dec
IR45468-B-12	Baisbish/IR56	245	12	180	240	9 Dec
RP2078-58-74-1	Mansarovar/CO 14	268	10	186	231	6 Dec
RF'2078-63-81-1	Mansarovar/CO 14	250	10	191	236	5 Dec
RP2078-56-71-39	Mansarovar/CO 14	269	10	195	237	6 Dec
Jalmagna	Pureline selection	290	13	196	233	2 Dec
NDGR1045-38-127-113	RP/LMN111	255	11	215	228	21 Nov

Internode length and three maximum elongating internodes.